

Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in a National High School

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Abstract:

This study aimed to assess the leadership skills of the school planning team (SPT) in a national high school for the School Year 2022–2023 as a basis for a management skills plan. Utilizing a descriptive research design, the study involved 127 teacher-respondents who answered a validated and reliable researcher-made questionnaire. It focused on three leadership areas: planning, organizational, and problem-solving skills. Data analysis employed descriptive, comparative, and analytical approaches, considering respondents' age, length of service, and position. Findings revealed that the SPT demonstrated a high level of leadership across all three areas, performing best in organizational skills and least in planning and problem-solving. When grouped by age, position, and service length, the leadership ratings remained consistently high, except for a significant difference in problem-solving skills based on length of service. Most respondents were young professionals under 41 years old, with bachelor's degrees and relatively new in the teaching profession. Despite their youth and varied roles, the SPT was perceived as effective in planning and organizing but needed improvement in problem-solving. The study recommended enhancing leadership skills through strategic planning, open communication, and healthy school relationships. It also encouraged the SPT to engage in leadership training and seminars to further develop their planning, organizational, and problem-solving capabilities.

Keywords: Leadership Skills, School Planning Team, Organizational Skills, Planning skills, Problem-solving Skills

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The Department of Education works to protect and promote the right of Filipinos to have a quality basic education that is equitable, culture-based, and complete that allows them to realize their potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. In addition, the said agency is responsible for ensuring teachers' professional development to increase and improve student learning outcomes (DepEd Order No. 35, S. 2016).

The Department of Education released a Division Memorandum No. 44 S. 2015 entitled "Guidelines on the Enhanced School Implementing Plan (SIP) Process and the School Report Card (SRC)." These guidelines are needed in the preparation of the SIP and SRC of the school. School Improvement Plan (SIP) is a roadmap that shows the specific interventions of the school together with the help of the stakeholders that will take effect within five consecutive years. This implementation plan is very crucial to prepare because of many branches to document in the process to complete it. The school planning team is the one who is responsible for preparing the plan to reach the goal of providing quality education, clean facilities, and a safe environment for teachers, staff, and students.

According to DepEd Order No. 45, S. 2015, under the Guidelines on School-Based Management (SBM) Grants, an effective School-Based Management (SBM) can be formed and has the capacity to develop programs and manage the school's own affairs and concerns. Since the school personnel in-charged in SBM are the same persons in School Planning Team (SPT), they need to reach the goals of SBM, and these include improving the teaching and learning experience in school, developing and enhancing the school management and administrative procedures, and to strengthen the resiliency of disadvantaged schools. The SBM and SPT are encouraged to

execute their leadership roles among the constituents and stakeholders to be at the forefront of school reforms and developments.

The agency is investing so much in teachers' quality of teaching and professional development in the service. The agency is continuously providing teachers with needed training and seminars to enhance their skills in different aspects, especially in leadership. Leadership skills are frequently assessed from the actions of the educational administrators and leaders of the school. Many factors are affected by their decisions and implementations, including the teaching, non-teaching personnel, and the students. The success and development of the school are primarily based on how they perform and contribute.

The School Principal heads the school planning team, followed by the Assistant School Principal, designated teachers as coordinator, co-coordinator, teacher representative, and SDRRMC. It also includes a parent representative, school governance council representative, LGU representative, BDRRMC, and SSG representative. The school planning team also has an expanded school planning team which includes the department head teachers in each subject, the administrative officer, administrative and accounting staff, and grade-level advisers. The school planning team is composed of knowledgeable leaders who possess enough skills to effectively implement their functions as it is the main foundation to achieve steps toward success.

This national high school is one of the compliant schools in one division of a highly urbanized city in Central Philippines, where the School Implementation Plan is fully implemented. The researcher, being a non-teaching personnel of the said school, has realized that some of her colleagues, teachers, non-teaching, and students still have a lot of concerns and suggestions on how the team comes up with plans, organizing or prioritizing different concerns, and solves the problems prior and after the plan is implemented.

Current State of Knowledge

Low performance in school often reflects the leadership skills of the school planning team, which may stem from limited supervisory, leadership, and interpersonal skills (Villanueva, Sanchez, et al., 2018). This observation aligns with broader leadership challenges faced across various sectors in the country.

In fact, Brillantes and Perante-Calina (2018) emphasized that leaders often struggle with excessive rules and regulations, inefficient procedures, corruption, and a lack of participation and coordination in public sector initiatives. Their study concluded that meaningful change begins with leaders themselves—by enhancing their own capacities and those of others, and by committing to continuous improvement.

Furthermore, a key aspect of effective leadership is communication. Brooks and Sutherland (2014) found that poor communication is a recurring issue among school heads in the Philippines. Limited dialogue between management and teachers hinders the sharing of ideas, suggestions, and best practices, ultimately affecting school performance.

In relation to this, Villanueva (2021) stressed that leadership requires specific traits and characteristics. Leadership has long been studied as a phenomenon capable of shaping or breaking environments. Some believe great leaders are born with innate traits, while others argue that leadership emerges through opportunity and circumstance—both perspectives are recognized in modern leadership thought.

Complementing these insights, Rodriguez (2020) outlined that effective leaders possess a clear vision, set goals, and actively engage their teams in achieving these objectives. Beyond planning and strategizing, successful leadership involves modeling exemplary behavior. When these qualities are applied with consistency and intention, they lead to impactful and transformative leadership.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on the Integrative Theory of Leadership by Chemers, M. (1997), that leadership is a process of influence in which a person can provide the needs and support of others to accomplish a common task. In addition, leadership is composed of group activity that is based on influence and is very complex. Thoughts and emotions need to coordinate with communication and actions to effectively have an impact on other people and subordinates.

An organization is composed of diverse people with different personalities, and the workplace is one of the common settings where diversity exists. Because of its diversity, educational leaders will find applicable leadership skills to blend and influence the school's teachers, staff, and students.

According to Chemers, M. (1997), every skill leaders possess has been developed from different activities they handled either in a team or individually to achieve the goals. They can come up with effective and efficient solutions to different problems that the school is facing. Their leadership skills and coordination will give the organization the courage and confidence to strive for the betterment of the school and will give them a clear vision and mission toward their goals. The said theory explains that as leaders of the organization, whatever

they think is right to do must coordinate with their actions. This could build trust and coordination within the organization.

Moreover, a lack of leadership skills will lead to risk factors in a team. A bad plan will break up a team or cause frustration to individuals, according to John Adair (2007). It will decrease the performance of an individual to a team and the engagement of employees, lack of decision making, failed outcome of projects and programs, unclear priorities and goals, and no backup plans.

Importance of leadership skills is as important as having a reliable and trusted team. A team in which members are cooperative, work hand in hand, listen well to people's concerns, are decisive, problem-solver, prioritize the organization's needs, and make many great plans for the organization's development are characteristics of leaders that an organization needs. This research focused on determining the level of leadership skills of the school planning team to determine their performance to various needs of the teachers, non-teaching personnel, students, and stakeholders.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team of a national high school during the School Year 2022-2023 as the basis for a management skills plan. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions: what is the profile of the teachers in terms of age, length of service, and plantilla position; what is the level of leadership skills of the School Planning Team according to the areas planning skills, organizational Skills, and problem-solving skills; is there a significant difference in the level of leadership skills of the School Planning Team as assessed by the teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, and based on the results of the study, what management skills plan can be formulated?

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design, data gathering procedure, other instrumentation, and statistical tools. It also discusses the parameters, especially the statistical tools, the respondents, and the study's locality.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive method research design that aims to describe the information from the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretation of evidence. This method provides accurate characteristics of an individual, situation, or group. It also determines the frequency and categorization of information. This method shows the relationships between or among the variables (Dulock, 2010). The descriptive method research design is suitable for determining the level of leadership skills of the school planning team as it provided facts and scientific judgment as the data came from the primary sources, who were the teachers.

Study Respondents

The data respondents were the 127 secondary teachers out of 188 of them from a national high school in a highly urbanized city in a medium-sized division in Negros Island Region during the School Year 2022-2023. Due to the many respondents, sampling was employed using Cochran's Formula to come up with the number of respondents in this study. To get the percentage, the respondents from each grade level were divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The respondents were randomly selected by the researchers from each grade level using the lottery technique.

Instrument

The researchers gathered the needed data for this study by constructing a research-made survey questionnaire to determine the level of leadership skills of the school planning team as the basis for a management skills plan. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, wherein Part I dealt with the profile of respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and plantilla position. Part II of the questionnaire covered 10 items for each area of planning, organizing, and problem-solving skills. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, using a 5-point Likert scale rating with 5 as "Always," 4 as "Often," 3 as "Sometimes," 2 as "Rarely," and 1 as "Almost Never."

Data Gathering and Procedure

After administering the validity and reliability, upon approval of the schools division superintendent, the questionnaires were administered to target respondents. The questionnaires were gathered, recorded, and analyzed. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The encoded data was computer processed using the SPSS.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1 and 2 employed a descriptive analytical scheme, using the frequency count and percentage as a statistical tool to assess the profile of respondents, mean to assess the level of leadership skills of the school planning team across the three areas. Objective 3 utilized a comparative analytical scheme, applying the Mann-Whitney U test to determine significant differences in the level of leadership skills of the school planning team when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

By guaranteeing the confidentiality of the respondents' answers and upholding their anonymity during the whole research process, the researchers made a concerted effort to reduce the possibility of harm to its target respondents in accordance with Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researchers also requested their free and informed consent up front.

Results and Discussion:

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered to carry out the predetermined objectives of this study.

Profile of Respondents

Table 1

Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 41 years old)	64	50.40
	Older (41 years old and above)	63	49.60
Length of Service	Shorter	69	54.30
	Longer	58	45.70
	Lower	68	53.5
Plantilla Position	Higher	59	46.5
	Total	127	100

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents of the study. The following variables are age, length of service, and the plantilla/position. Each variable is then sub-classified by the following parameters, namely: categories, frequency, percentage, and the total. It is seen from the figures that the respondents come from two groups, younger (below 41 years old) with a frequency of 64 and a percentage of 50.40, while the older (41 years old and above) with a frequency of 63 and a percentage of 49.60 a with a total of 127, 69 of them have shorter in the length of service with a percentage of 54.30 and 58 of them have a longer length of service with a percentage of 45.70 with a total of 127 and a percentage of 100 showing that respondents who have a shorter length of service have higher numerical values. As for the plantilla/ position, the lower category has a frequency of 68 or 53.5%, which is classified as Teacher I and Teacher II, while the higher category has a frequency of 59 or 46.5%, classified as Teacher III, Master Teacher I, or II. Thus, for a plantilla/ position, the lower category is higher than that of, the higher one. All in all, each variable arrives at the same total in terms of frequency and percentage.

The data indicate that the majority of the respondents are below 41 years old or younger, and more teachers have a shorter length of service. In addition, the majority of the respondents are Teachers I and II. As supported by the findings of Lubsky, A. V., & Chikarova, G. I. (2021), young teachers play an important role in the development of general education. They are a social group who have lots of interests and values to make significant contributions to the field of teaching. Their modern ideas and way of teaching can help students learn the lessons easily. They also have a vital role in encouraging students to pursue and reach their dreams.

In a public school, applicants must have three or more years of experience as one of the qualifications before entering the field of teaching. Some young professionals prefer to work in a private academy and spend three or more years teaching before going to public school. Some stay at private schools because they find a workplace where they feel comfortable and happy.

According to the study by Kilic (2017), some companies hire younger employees than older ones because they are associated with greater productivity and have lots of inputs and modern ideas in the industry. They are a model of investment where young and experienced employees are equipped with roles, have a broader perspective, and are significant in the workplace.

In Plantilla/Position, the majority of the respondents are from lower-level positions, as represented by Teachers I and II. The result of the study indicates that Teacher I may have needed more teaching experience, which requires three years and inclusivity in various seminars and training to be promoted. In addition, Teacher II may have been inactive in training, professional development, and research which are some of the bases to be upgraded to a higher position.

Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team

Table 2

Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in the Area Planning Skills

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Planning Skills		
The School Planning Team ...		
1. possesses the capacity to carry out a plan.	4.32	High Level
2. is open to teachers and staff's requests and concerns.	4.22	High Level
3. plans by the school's vision.	4.43	High Level
4. has alternative plans or strategies in case of setbacks.	4.17	High Level
5. makes sure that the plan will achieve the desired outcomes.	4.29	High Level
6. possesses healthy communication skills.	4.30	High Level
7. explores new avenues for implementing the plan.	4.15	High Level
8. analyzes the process from all perspectives.	4.24	High Level
9. considers the team members' input at each level of the planning process.	4.31	High Level
10. examines the plan for any gaps or problems that could lead to potential difficulties.	4.21	High Level
Overall Mean	4.26	High Level

Table 2 shows the level of leadership skills of the school planning team according to the area of planning skills with an overall mean of 4.26, interpreted as a high level. Item number 3, "plans by the school's vision," obtained the highest mean of 4.43 interpreted as high level, while item number 7, "explores new avenues for implementing the plan" obtained the lowest mean of 4.15, interpreted as high level.

This result means that the School Planning Team needs to explore all avenues to implement various plans for the development of the school and address other school-related concerns. The result is linked to the study of Bitterova, Hakova, and Pisonova (2014), Slovakia states that leadership skills in terms of planning are significant to the better and more effective performance of their mandate. The school planning team's character, performance, and competencies are reflected based on the learning environment of educational institutions and the success of the implemented programs and projects. Together with the effort of the stakeholders, they are the ones preparing, implementing, and thinking about new strategies to develop effective learning methods and modules, and practices. In this case, the team may find more ways or alternative solutions to make the plan possible. The cooperation and coordination of the team are needed to make the plan and implementation successful.

The School Heads are also important people to help and take part in this function: The School Planning Team which is composed of teachers, students, and various organization representatives.

Table 3

Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in the Area Organizational Skills

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Organizational Skills		
The School Planning Team ...		
1. works well under pressure.	4.39	High Level
2. assign tasks to help people improve their abilities.	4.40	High Level
3. communicates well in the workplace.	4.24	High Level
4. has a goal-oriented attitude in making decisions.	4.35	High Level
5. delegates work responsibilities.	4.40	High Level
6. informs staff members of plans and actions.	4.26	High Level
7. involves keeping a detailed calendar.	4.22	High Level
8. directs communication with individuals.	4.28	High Level
9. motivates you to be diligent and precise in your work.	4.32	High Level
10. maintains composure under pressure.	4.35	High Level
Overall Mean	4.32	High Level

As shown in Table 3, the level of leadership skills of the School Planning Team in the area of organizational skills with an overall mean of 4.32, interpreted as high level. Item number 2, "assign tasks to help people improve their abilities," and item number 5, "delegates work responsibilities," have the same mean of 4.40, interpreted

as a high level, while item number 7, "involves keeping a detailed calendar" has the lowest mean of 4.22 but still interpreted as high level.

The school is one of the busiest institutions in the public sector, where teachers are busy working with lesson plans, blended learning modality, making activities for students, and other school-related work. This result shows that keeping a detailed calendar has been given less priority by the school planning team, which may have been the cause of the delay in solving school-related concerns. Some members may often need to remember the agenda to open up with the team. Having a traditional calendar or a modern one like Google Calendar may help the team be organized in the discussion and prioritization of matters that can give the right amount of services that the school needs.

According to the study of A. McDonald et al. (2011), Google Calendar or keeping a detailed calendar can help professionals be more effective in their fields. Makany, Kemp, and Dror (2009) studied that taking notes is very important for academic and commercial use and success. According to their data analysis, note-takers were significantly better in terms of the quantity and quality of the learned material than those who were not. Using non-linear note-taking or linear note-taking techniques enables the person to have a deeper understanding and more integrated knowledge management. With this, a person who is always keeping notes, especially in planning in the management, will avoid the disorganization of plans.

Table 4

Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in the Area Problem-Solving Skills

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Problem-Solving Skills		
The School Planning Team ...		
1. generates the solution efficiently.	4.24	High Level
2. resolves problems quickly and successfully.	4.16	High Level
3. analyzes problems with the teachers and staff.	4.30	High Level
4. describes the issue or problem we are attempting to tackle.	4.27	High Level
5. seeks other alternative solutions.	4.29	High Level
6. resolves conflict effectively.	4.27	High Level
7. makes sensible and reasonable decisions.	4.35	High Level
8. effectively implements the solution that was chosen.	4.27	High Level
9. considers the nature of the issue and the best tool to address it.	4.25	High Level
10. listens and considers all of the arguments from all sides before making a decision.	4.18	High Level
Overall Mean	4.26	High Level

This table presents the level of leadership skills of the School Planning team in the area of problem-solving skills with an overall mean of 4.26 as interpreted as a high level. The highest mean is 4.35 in item number 7, "makes sensible and reasonable decisions." In contrast, item number 2, "resolves problems quickly and successfully," has the lowest mean of 4.16, which is still interpreted as a high level.

This denotes that the school planning team may have needed to be more efficient and more effective in some cases when dealing with and solving problems. They have to take a long time to decide on various matters concerning the school. Leading an organization is an eggshell; however, the teachers, students, and stakeholders commonly depend on the team's steps. Since leading the school with a team requires a lot of meetings and agreements between the members to come up with a decision or action, and this has been a problem for the school planning team.

The American Association of School Administrators (Hoyle et al., 1995) claims that if schools are to become a reality, every person in the district or school must become linked to continuous improvement efforts. The administrators or leaders and staff should always work together, discuss some issues that need to be solved, and be ready to make efforts for the development of the organization as well as the ability of every individual in the institution.

According to the study of Brooks and Sutherland (2014), communication is one of the problems of school heads in the Philippines. Communication is part of leadership. There needs to be more communication between the management and teachers. This prevents them from sharing their ideas, suggestions, and best practices with the school. With this, it is important to encourage every team member to express their ideas and offer suggestions because open communication with the team can help resolve problems quickly and successfully.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in the Area Planning Skills

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	64	59.53	1730.000	0.166		Not Significant
	Older	63	68.54				
Length of Service	Shorter	69	60.98	1792.500	0.310	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	58	67.59				
Plantilla Position	Lower	68	63.07	1943.000	0.759		Not Significant
	Higher	59	65.07				

Table 5 shows the level of leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of planning skills when grouped and compared according to variables, age, length of service, and plantilla position with a p-value of 0.166, 0.310, and 0.759, which are greater than the significance value of 0.05.

The stated hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the level of leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of planning skills when grouped and compared to variables” is not rejected.

As indicated in the result, the teachers can see the school planning team’s capability to decide, implement programs, develop strategies, and lead the school for improvement. They are working based on their functions and roles in the team.

Rodriguez (2020) outlined the characteristics of a leader. According to him, the characteristics of a leader are to have a vision, some goals, or some objectives. The second step is to explain that objective to the other team members and to get their support for such goals. The third step is to create and carry out a strategy to achieve that objective. Only some receive leadership training, either directly or indirectly. When these qualities are carefully applied, good leadership results. Providing an excellent example is likely the most crucial leadership quality.

Table 6
Difference in the Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in the Area Organizational Skills

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	64	58.95	1692.500	0.115		Not Significant
	Older	63	69.13				
Length of Service	Shorter	69	58.38	1613.000	0.058	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	58	70.69				
Plantilla Position	Lower	68	60.96	1799.500	0.313		Not Significant
	Higher	59	67.50				

Table 6 shows the level of leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of organizational skills when grouped and compared according to variables, age, length of service, and plantilla position with a p-value of 0.115, 0.058, and 0.313, which are greater than the significance value of 0.05.

The stated hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the level of leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of organizational skills when grouped and compared to variables” is not rejected.

The result shows the school planning team works well under pressure and has a goals-oriented attitude in making decisions. The government governs public schools, and as we know, most public schools need to be better-maintained regarding physical facilities and structures. However, thanks to the school planning team around the Philippines which has impacted all learners, teachers, and staff.

According to the study by Brillantes and Perante-Calina (2018), this country's leaders face many problems, such as excessive rules and regulations, inefficient procedures, corruption, and lack of participation and coordination in programs and projects of the public sector. The study concluded that leaders could make great changes by developing and enhancing the capacities of themselves first and others, they should also push themselves to sustain improvement. According to the said DepEd Order No. 44, S. 2015, though many problems arise in school, they always remember to motivate the students, teachers, and staff to be diligent and precise in their respective work. Aiming for success in every plan, the team may assign tasks to teachers who have their trust to finish it effectively by this, and the teachers will largely improve their abilities and skills in service delivery and school management. The priority for improvement is based on the disparity of the school’s goals, urgency, feasibility, and strategic importance.

Table 7
Difference in the Level of Leadership Skills of the School Planning Team in the Area Problem-Solving Skills

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	64	58.85	1686.500	0.108		Not Significant
	Older	63	69.23				
Length of Service	Shorter	69	57.66	1563.500	0.032	0.05	Significant
	Longer	58	71.54				
Plantilla Position	Lower	68	62.06	1874.000	0.519		Not Significant
	Higher	59	66.24				

Table 7 shows the level of leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of problem-solving skills when grouped and compared according to variables, age, length of service, and plantilla position with a p-value of 0.108, 0.519, shows no significant difference which is greater than the significance value of 0.05, classified as not rejected and p-value of 0.032, shows significant which is lower than the significance value of 0.05, classified as rejected.

The stated hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of problem-solving skills when grouped and compared according to age and plantilla position" is not rejected.

However, when teachers are grouped and compared according to the length of service, there is a significant difference in the level of leadership skills of the school planning team when they are grouped and compared according to the length of service. Hence, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the leadership skills of the school planning team in the area of problem-solving skills when grouped and compared according to the length of service" is rejected.

This indicates that the problem-solving skills of the school planning team need to fully convince male and female teachers who are new or tenured in service. This result requires the planning team to enhance their problem-solving skills to generate the solutions effectively and efficiently, needs to seek other alternative solutions right away when the plan fails or is not implemented, and they must also to consider the arguments from all sides before making a decision. However, the Department of Education holds seminars and workshops to improve the different skills of teachers, including problem-solving skills.

Low performance in school reflects on the leadership skills of the school planning team emanating from the scarcity of supervisory, leadership, and interpersonal skills, according to Villanueva, Sanchez, et al. (2018).

Conclusion:

The respondents in this study were mostly new in the field of teaching, young professionals, and most of them finished their schooling in their undergraduate studies. In general, the school planning team's leadership skills were high in all areas: planning, organizational, and problem-solving skills. The school planning team attained a high level of planning, organization, and problem-solving skills by both younger and older respondents. They also scored high in planning, organizational, and problem-solving skills regardless of respondents' length of service in school. For lower and higher positions, the team obtained a high level of leadership skills in planning, organizational, and problem-solving skills. Finally, it concluded that the problem-solving skills of the school planning team could have been more effective based on the respondents' length of service (shorter or longer). Moreover, the planning skills and organizational skills were implied effectively regardless of the respondents' age, length of service, and plantilla/positions.

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